

BioValue

Impacts of Economic and Financial Instruments on Biodiversity in Spatial Planning

D3.2: Impacts of E&FIs on biodiversity in spatial planning
WP 3, T 3.2

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1. Introduction

The BioValue project aims to safeguard and enhance biodiversity from a transformative change perspective by better articulating 1) spatial planning instruments, 2) environmental assessment instruments, and 3) economic and financial instruments (E&FIs) during the spatial planning process; and explores how the three instrumental perspectives interact in practice to enable transformative change through three Arenas for Transformation in Portugal (the Municipality of Mafra), Italy (the Municipality of Trento), and Germany (the Federal State of Mecklenburg-Vorpommern). In particular, Work Package 3 (WP3) focuses on understanding the transformative potential of E&FIs impacting biodiversity, individually and in articulation with spatial planning and environmental assessment instruments, across different levels of implementation.

This report belongs to a series of deliverables documenting the research work carried out under the four subtasks of WP3. Prior to this report, we have conducted analyses of E&FIs that enhance biodiversity outcomes- Task 3.1, see [BioValue Report D3.1: Economic and Financial Instruments to Enhance Biodiversity](#)), where we reviewed the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 to understand the implications of EU biodiversity policy for spatial planning; and analysed 24 generic biodiversity-promoting E&FIs identified by the Ecosystem Opportunity Framework (Rode et al., 2016) with criteria of their relevance to spatial planning along the Mitigation Hierarchy.

The recent Eklipse² report on the Mitigation Hierarchy recommended the use of a mix of mandatory and voluntary instruments, e.g., taxation, to avoid or minimise negative impacts on biodiversity in land-use planning processes for authorities at different scales in order to protect valuable habitats (Savilaakso et al., 2023), highlighting the high potential of incorporating appropriate E&FIs into land-use planning. Through a systematic mapping of existing research on using the concept of ecosystem services/natural capital to enhance biodiversity in planning processes, the Eklipse report identified several factors that lead to the neglect of ecosystem services benefits, e.g., lack of stakeholder engagement, underestimation of the value of biodiversity by the private sector, overlooking of ecosystem services by landowners when benefits accrue to others, and insufficient explicit consideration of ecosystem services benefits in either Strategic Environmental Assessment or Environmental Impact Assessment (Savilaakso et al., 2023). As the mechanism of E&FIs is to motivate behavioural changes by revealing and internalising the full economic and environmental costs and benefits among the various beneficiaries, polluters, and managers of ecosystems (IPBES, 2018), the inclusion of E&FIs can be of interest not only for the decision-making authorities, but also for the other actors involved in the spatial planning processes and environmental assessment. However, there is a paucity of research that systematically discusses the current status, potential, and possible approaches of integrating E&FIs into spatial planning processes and environmental assessment.

This report documents the research work conducted under Task 3.2, WP3, which aims to understand the current impact of E&FIs outcomes on biodiversity in the context of spatial planning and environmental assessment. The structure of the report is as follows: [Section 2](#) reviews the current application of E&FIs in spatial planning and analyses the position of E&FIs for enhancing

² Eklipse is a European science-policy interface mechanism created in 2016 to help different stakeholders, such as governments, institutions, businesses and NGOs, make better-informed decisions for biodiversity. More information see: <http://www.eklipse.eu/>.

biodiversity in practice with selected spatial planning instruments; [Section 3](#) provides an overview of E&FI recommendations in the benchmark of environmental assessments, and describes the focus for analysing the use of E&FIs in environmental assessment projects; [Section 4](#) discusses how E&FIs enhancing biodiversity can be positioned with examples of impact pathways towards transformative change; and [Section 5](#) summarises the main findings under Task 3.2.

2. Economic and Financial Instruments in Spatial Planning

Application of E&FIs in Spatial Planning

E&FIs in spatial planning are mainly used to manage the trade-offs between environmental, economic, and social objectives. In particular, E&FIs have been commonly employed to internalise the benefits and costs of development in the form of various land value capture tools, e.g. recurring land value tax or building value tax, betterment levies, land value increment tax, sale of development rights, recurring lease payments, etc. (Halleux et al., 2022; Kamiya & Zhang, 2017). With land value capture tools, local governments may levy fees and taxes on developers and landowners to generate revenue that can be used to fund civic and municipal services. A community can recuperate and reinvest increases in land value generated by public investment and other government initiatives through the land value capture tools. It is often applied in urban areas, particularly in the context of development (Halleux et al., 2022). Table 1 provides an overview of the most commonly used land value tools and explains how they work in spatial planning (Gerber et al., 2018; Gielen & van der Krabben, 2019; Halleux et al., 2022; Hong & Needham, 2007; OECD & Lincoln Institute of Land Policy, 2022).

Table 1: Overview of land value capture tools in spatial planning

Instrument	Form	How it works in spatial planning
Infrastructure levy/ Betterment contributions	Taxes; Fees	Tax or fee levied on landowners possessing land that has gained in value due to infrastructure investment initiated by the government.
Developer obligations	Impact fees; Exactions; Development charges	Cash or in-kind contributions that support costs for additional infrastructure or services that need to be provided due to private development. Unlike the infrastructure levy, developer obligations are triggered by the initiative of private developers and land owners and mainly apply when developers seek development approval or special permissions. Developers are subject to obligations to obtain approval for new developments or densification. The obligations consist of cash or in-kind payments or a combination of both. Besides common developer obligations such as impact fees, negotiated exactions, or development charges, in some countries, developers can also be required to build affordable housing (a practice called inclusionary zoning) or sustainable mobility infrastructures in exchange for building permits.

Charges for development rights	Fees; In-kind contributions	Cash or in-kind contributions that are payable in exchange for development rights above a set density baseline defined by a jurisdictional ordinance or regulation. Thus, predefined land-use and zoning regulations that set baseline and maximum densities are required. Developers may also be charged for development rights when governments alter zoning or relax density regulations. In some cases, limited development rights, for example, in protected environmental areas, can be transferred to a different plot better suited to higher-density development. Usually, the types and amounts of cash or in-kind charges are defined in advance in ordinances or local regulations. Related terms include the sale of development rights, the sale of air rights, and the transfer of building rights.
Land readjustment	Compensation fees; In-kind contributions	Urban development method that implies the property structure transformation (with owners transferring a portion of their land for public use), and an equitable distribution of the development benefits and costs to all participants according to their initial contributions (more commonly land parcels). In most cases, land readjustment can be initiated by local governments or private landowners.

Using the same set of criteria that we developed for the analysis of E&FIs enhancing biodiversity in Task 3.1 (see [BioValue Report D3.1: Economic and Financial Instruments to Enhance Biodiversity](#)), we categorised the four types of land value capture tools (as shown in Tables 2 and 3) with examples of application in different countries, including the countries where the BioValue Arenas for Transformations are located (see [Annex I](#)).

Table 2: Characteristics of land value capture tools in spatial planning- instrument specificities

Instrument	Scale of implementation	Scale of legislation origin	Main actors involved as payers	Source of finance
Infrastructure levy/ Betterment contributions	Neighbourhood, Municipal, Intermunicipal, Regional, National	Municipal, Regional, National	Land and property owners, Leaseholders	Private- property developers, Private- individuals
Developer obligations	Neighbourhood, Municipal	Municipal, National	Landowners, Private developers	Private- property developers, Private- landowners

Charges for development rights	Neighbourhood, Municipal	Municipal, Regional, National	Landowners, Private developers	Private- property developers, Private- individuals
Land readjustment	Neighbourhood, Municipal	Municipal, National	Landowners, Private developers	Public, Private- property developers, Private- landowners

Table 3: Characteristics of land value capture tools in spatial planning- roles in spatial planning

Instrument	Area of application	Land ownership	Nature of implementation
Infrastructure levy/ Betterment contributions	Urban, Peri-urban, Rural	Private	Government-led
Developer obligations	Urban, Peri-urban, Rural	Private	Government-led
Charges for development rights	Urban, Peri-urban, Rural,	Private	Government-led
Land readjustment	Urban, Peri-urban, Rural	Private, Public	Government-led (private entities, private landowners and stakeholders with claims towards the affected land)

(continued table)

Instrument	Approaching strategy	Main interaction stage	Cross-authority collaboration
Infrastructure levy/ Betterment contributions	Top-down	4- Implementation of plans/policies	Yes
Developer obligations	Top-down	4- Implementation of plans/policies	Yes
Charges for development rights	Top-down	4- Implementation of plans/policies	Yes
Land readjustment	Top-down	4- Implementation of plans/policies	Yes

The land value capture tools share similar logic with E&FIs enhancing biodiversity. Both instruments aim to reveal the hidden benefits and costs of either development and public infrastructure investments (in the case of land value capture tools) or biodiversity and ecosystem services (in the case of E&FIs enhancing biodiversity), and to address externalities. Compared to

the various E&FIs enhancing biodiversity³ that can be adopted at different levels, land value capture tools are typically applied at a lower administrative level (i.e. neighbourhood and municipal levels), with the exception of the infrastructure levy/ betterment contributions, which can be applied at all levels. Land value capture tools are commonly targeted at landowners and private developers to raise money from private sectors to compensate for public services, and are therefore government-led through a top-down strategy. Similar to most E&FIs enhancing biodiversity, the main interaction stage of land value capture tools in the spatial planning cycle is at the plan/policy implementation stage and requires cross-authority collaborations.

While land value capture tools are the typical E&FIs used in spatial planning for land-based financing, recent literature increasingly discusses the potential of E&FIs to facilitate the implementation of Nature-based Solutions in cities to achieve inclusiveness or affordability goals (Longato et al., 2023; Mendonça et al., 2021; Trinomics & IUCN, 2019). In principle, all land value capture tools can be used for promoting biodiversity, as the funds raised from landowners and private developers can be allocated for public services, including the implementation of Nature-based Solutions or other biodiversity and ecosystem purposes. In addition to the land value capture tools, the E&FIs recommended in the literature to facilitate the adoption of Nature-based Solutions in cities, under the generic term, are summarised in Table 3.

Table 4: E&FIs to facilitate the implementation of Nature-based Solutions in cities

Instrument	How it works in spatial planning
User fees & surcharges	Fees for the use of green space facilities, e.g., entrance fees for parks (Trinomics & IUCN, 2019)
Biodiversity offsets, habitat/mitigation banking	Compensation obligations in development through biodiversity offsets and habitat banking; Funds linked to compensation requirements, e.g., the compensation payments from developments under requirement are pooled into a fund that is used to finance nature conservation projects (Longato et al., 2023; Trinomics & IUCN, 2019)
Green credit & loans	Cities can apply for low-interest loans from public or private financial institutions for projects with environmental and/or social benefits (Longato et al., 2023; Trinomics & IUCN, 2019) Green credit and credit trading schemes, e.g. an overall pollution target or a stormwater management target set by local authorities, with credits distributed to relevant economic actors to reduce pollution or encourage the installation of green infrastructure for runoff mitigation (Trinomics & IUCN, 2019)
Green investment facilities (conservation bonds, green investment funds, blended finance, etc.)	A Municipal Green Bond, where the municipality commits to using proceeds only for environmentally beneficial projects (Kamiya & Zhang, 2017) The Natural Capital Financing Facility for projects with a focus on nature and biodiversity and ecosystem-based adaptation

³ In Task 3.1, we analysed 24 generic E&FIs enhancing biodiversity with their relevance to spatial planning originally identified by Rode et al. (2016). For more information see: [BioValue Report D3.1: Economic and Financial Instruments to Enhance Biodiversity](#).

	to climate change, including projects in cities (Trinomics & IUCN, 2019)
Taxes	Taxes and charges on the grey infrastructure and activities detrimental to green infrastructure to promote and maintain green infrastructure (Trinomics & IUCN, 2019)
Tax reliefs, subsidies	Subsidies on the installation of green infrastructure on private property; tax rebates for private green spaces (Trinomics & IUCN, 2019)
Payments for Ecosystem Services	PES schemes involving land owners for the provision of ecosystem services (Trinomics & IUCN, 2019)
Allocation of land/resource management & usage rights	Local authorities can pay landowners to give up development rights, transferring ownership from the landowner to a public body or organisation, or they can allow developers to build in another area or sell the development rights in exchange for protecting the original area from development (Longato et al., 2023)
Privately protected areas & Conservation easements	Legal agreement on the land to restrict the development, management or use of the land, including voluntary sale or gift of one or more rights by the landowner to a public body or organisation (Longato et al., 2023)
Environmental training & education programmes	Guidelines and criteria for the design and management of public spaces; promotion of best practices and techniques for use in private landowners' areas (Longato et al., 2023)

E&FIs for Promoting Biodiversity in Selected Spatial Planning Instruments

Within BioValue activities, an in-depth analysis of 28 spatial planning instruments in seven countries (Italy, Denmark, Germany, Portugal, Scotland, Spain, and Switzerland) was conducted to assess the transformative potential of four different spatial planning systems in T1.1, WP1 (analysis led by the research team from the University of Trento, for more information see: [BioValue Report D1.1: Current Challenges and Barriers to Biodiversity Inclusion in SP&MI](#)). The analysis presented in the BioValue Report D1.1 follows a conceptual framework that identifies four characteristics of transformative change for biodiversity in relation to four components of spatial planning instruments and four elements of analysis of spatial planning systems. In particular, the components of spatial planning instruments include visions, strategies, information baseline, and actions/regulations/instruments stated in the planning documents.

In T3.2, WP3, we extract the original data⁴ generated by the in-depth analysis of the transformative elements for biodiversity on “actions/regulations/instruments” from the 28 selected spatial planning instruments, and analyse the relevance of E&FIs in practice. In total, we obtain 193 lines from 25 spatial planning instruments on “actions/regulations/instruments”. An overview of the 25 spatial planning instruments can be found in [Annex II](#).

⁴ Page 44-252, Appendix B, [BioValue Report D1.1: Current Challenges and Barriers to Biodiversity Inclusion in SP&MI](#)

Most of the spatial planning instruments (19 out of 25) promote ecological solutions for biodiversity-integrated planning, e.g., the *Urban Plan of Bologna Municipality* integrates green roofs and walls, and the creation of public green spaces into urban planning, and implements measures, such as improved path connections to neighbouring green spaces for citizens, to strengthen ecological connectivity and ecosystem services. Many spatial planning instruments (12 out of 25) emphasise the role of regulations in the process, e.g., the *Territorial Metropolitan Plan of Bologna* mandates the improvement of pedestrian routes with green elements in urban redevelopment and promotes the reclamation of urban brownfields to enhance ecosystem services. Some spatial planning instruments (11 out of 25) include the development or use of guidelines for practices, e.g., the *General Urban Development Plan of Vittoria-Gasteiz* refers to a practical guideline for assessing the impacts of planning actions on public health. Some spatial planning instruments (7 out of 25) underline stakeholder participation in planning, e.g., the *Partial Territorial Plan of Central Álava* develops a participatory guideline for inclusive participation of stakeholders from government, institutions, and civil societies. In the spatial planning instruments reviewed, other aspects such as knowledge and data, necessary monitoring processes, cross-sectoral and cross-scale collaboration, and general awareness raising and education are also mentioned to varying degrees of priority.

Among the 25 spatial planning instruments, four documents from two countries (Portugal and Scotland) explicitly state the use of E&FI for promoting biodiversity-integrated planning. Table 5 presents an overview of the E&FIs mentioned in the spatial planning instruments under the generic terms defined in T3.1 with their main interaction stage on the Mitigation Hierarchy (MH).

Table 5: E&FI application in reviewed spatial planning instruments

Country	Spatial Planning Instrument	Year	E&FI	How it works	Main interaction stage on MH
Portugal	Regional Program of the Lisbon Metropolitan Area	2002	Privately protected areas (PPAs) & Conservation easements	The plan encourages municipalities to acquire lands or establish agreements with landowners to ensure public use of certain areas for the Metropolitan Ecologic Structure as part of the municipal heritage.	Avoid
Portugal	Management Plan of the Arrábida Natural Park	2005	Certification & eco-labelling; Environmental training & education programmes	Following the management plan, the Arrábida Natural Park collaborates with local farmers to establish agreements on revitalising traditional agricultural practices, in order to reduce chemical product reliance and to enhance the natural value of the land by facilitating product	Minimise

				certification and awareness-raising programmes.	
Scotland	National Planning Framework	2023	Green investment facilities (conservation bonds, green investment funds, blended finance, etc.)	The plan defines a Clyde Mission that brings together public and private funding to regenerate and revitalise brownfield sites along the River Clyde. In line with the Clyde Mission, a Clyde Mission Fund has been established to channel £10 million of capital funding in 2020-21 to support capital projects with environmental benefits.	Restore
Scotland	Cairngorms National Park Local Development Plan 2020	2020	Biodiversity offsets, habitat/ mitigation banking	The plan establishes a series of guidelines to promote responsible development and conservation, e.g., if ancient semi-natural woodland needs to be removed, the plan requires developers to compensate by planting native species elsewhere.	Offset

It is possible that, among the 25 spatial planning instruments from seven countries, there are documents other than the four above that include the application of E&FIs but were not captured by the initial in-depth analysis in T1.1, WP1. However, out of almost 200 lines describing actions, instruments, and regulations that promote biodiversity, less than 10 lines include E&FIs. The use of E&FIs to enhance biodiversity outcomes in spatial planning is not widespread in the selected examples.

In addition to the four planning documents that explicitly mention the use of E&FIs, there is further potential for the application of E&FIs within the spatial planning instruments reviewed, as some planning instruments highlight the need for funding for compensation measures or collective welfare. Many of the spatial planning instruments reviewed also consider ecosystem services. If the relevant stewards and beneficiaries (or sometimes polluters) of these ecosystem services can be identified through a thorough context analysis, appropriate E&FIs can potentially be designed.

3. Economic and Financial Instruments in Environmental Assessment

Under the BioValue project, an analysis to benchmark the best practice in environmental assessment instruments was carried out in T2.1, WP2 (analysis led by the research team from Aalborg University, see [BioValue Report D2.1: Benchmark for integration of biodiversity in Environmental Assessment Instruments](#)). In total, 12 guidance documents from 2006 to 2020 were analysed to understand the benchmark of the environmental assessment instruments. However, only four documents provide recommendations on the use of E&FIs, respectively:

- 1) *Best practice guidance for biodiversity-inclusive impact assessment*, published by the Capacity Building in Biodiversity and Impact Assessment project of the International Association for Impact Assessment (CBBIA-IAIA) in 2007;
- 2) *The Relationship between Biodiversity Offsets and Impact Assessment*, published by the Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme (BBOP) in 2009;
- 3) *International Best Practice Principles – Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services in Impact Assessment*, published by the International Association for Impact Assessment (IAIA) in 2018;
- 4) *Guidance Note for Standard 3 on Biodiversity and Ecosystems*, published by the European Investment Bank (EIB) in 2018.

The recommendations on E&FIs in the four documents focus on ensuring the availability of financial resources for the implementation of conservation measures, e.g., the guidance note provided by EIB also emphasises that the biodiversity-related financing should be discussed at the project appraisal stage. The CBBIA-IAIA Best Practice Guidance is the first guide to include E&FI considerations and provides the most detailed recommendations and concrete E&FI suggestions. It provides examples of guiding questions for analysing the relevance of incorporating E&FIs from the design stage, such as whether the project identifies the costs to be avoided, the benefits to be enhanced, and their potential equitable distribution. The guidance emphasises local cooperation on biodiversity through partnerships with the private sectors and the rationale of the 'polluter pays' and 'beneficiary pays' principles. Although the 'steward earns' principle is not explicitly mentioned in the document, the guide suggests measures, such as using project revenues to compensate for conservation, that touch on the principle. Several E&FIs are referred to in the guidance document under different circumstances. Under the generic E&FI terms defined in T3.1, these E&FIs are:

- 1) Benefit/revenue-sharing;
- 2) User fees & surcharges;
- 3) Taxes;
- 4) Green investment facilities (conservation bonds, green investment funds, blended finance, etc.);
- 5) Certification & eco-labelling;
- 6) Biodiversity offsets, habitat/ mitigation banking.

In general, the benchmarking analysis of environmental assessments shows a lack of guidance on measures at the avoidance stage, with most addressing the later stages of the mitigation hierarchy. Details of all the 12 guidance documents analysed and the associated E&FI elements are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Overview of E&FI recommendations in the guidance documents for environmental assessments

Title	How should E&FIs be used to assess or mitigate biodiversity in environmental assessment instruments?	Source
Voluntary Guidelines on Biodiversity-inclusive Environmental Impact Assessment	NA	CBD, 2006
Guidance Document on Biodiversity, Impact Assessment and Decision Making in Southern Africa	NA	CBBIA – IAIA, 2006
Best Practice Guidance for Biodiversity-inclusive Impact Assessment	<p>Questions that should be asked about a project: Does the project provide to compensate the affected local people by allocating some of its outputs (e.g. water for irrigation, thermal-hydro power) or otherwise invest in better livelihood of the project affected persons? Does the intended project identify how costs can be avoided, benefits increased or more equitably distributed?</p> <p>Building partnerships for enhancing biodiversity conservation in habitats on private land.</p> <p>The real rationale for compensation emerges from a principled foundation, namely the proverbial “polluter or damager pays principle”.</p> <p>Compensation for biodiversity, ecosystems and ecosystem services can be designed through the revenues of the project in monetary or non-monetary forms. Such measures can be either in cash or in-kind or both.</p> <p>As the polluter or damager pays principle suggests, it is possible to impose on the project beneficiary user fees, taxes and charges or a combination depending on the circumstance. There is a growing need to explore and integrate these economic measures into environmental management plans, for example through</p>	CBBIA – IAIA, 2007

	<p>the imposition of a tax for securing funding for compensation, minimisation, rehabilitation and restoration efforts.</p> <p>Environmental bonds can ensure that the project beneficiary takes adequate measures to minimise damage caused to biodiversity and ecosystems by their activities; clean up and restore residual damage in the most cost-effective manner; and have adequate funds available for clean-up and restoration if the project beneficiary fails comply. Environmental funds are financial instruments used for managing financial resources and disbursing these for initiatives that help conserves biodiversity. Environmental funds can be used to finance many initiatives including impact mitigation, research, data collection, monitoring, short-term or long-term training, public awareness and pro-poor conservation and development.</p> <p>Labelling and certification is an innovative measure to create a link between the demand and supply side of the market and establish an advantage for those who preserve biodiversity by labelling their products. The advantage of this type of measure is that it provides the project proponent with an incentive to minimise impacts. Furthermore, the increase in marginal revenues from labelling schemes can be used to secure funding for compensation, rehabilitation and restoration efforts.</p> <p>Tradable rights, offsets and concessions: In this context, these measures are essentially the rights to trade uses of biodiversity and ecosystem services. From the 'sellers' perspective, in this case the local community or communities or the state, trade away the rights to ecosystem resource use for compensation.</p>	
The Relationship between Biodiversity Offsets and Impact Assessment	Consider possible needs for finances to support offsets as well as possible need for land procurement of negotiations with landowners.	BBOP, 2009

	Ensuring long-term success requires significant changes to the ways in which Impact Assessment is practiced, e.g. through the introduction of rigorous finance mechanisms to support maintenance in perpetuity.	
Final Report: Integrated Biodiversity Impact Assessment, Streamlining AA, SEA and EIA Processes. Best Practice Guidance	NA	Irish EPA, 2012
Guidance on Integrating Climate Change and Biodiversity into Environmental Impact Assessment	NA	EC, 2013
Guidance on Integrating Climate Change and Biodiversity into Strategic Environmental Assessment	NA	EC, 2013
Good Practices for Biodiversity Inclusive Impact Assessment and Management Planning	NA	MFIBG, 2015
International Best Practice Principles – Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services in Impact Assessment	Ensure that the adequate financial provision is made to cover predicted costs of implementing all planned measures to mitigate impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services.	IAIA, 2018
Guidance Note for Standard 3 on Biodiversity and Ecosystems	The need for funds, legal frameworks and institutional capacity to be planned well in advance so that they are in place to allow offset implementation to begin in advance of significant impacts from the project – biodiversity-related finance should therefore be discussed during the appraisal stage	EIB, 2018
Best Practices for Publishing Biodiversity Data from Environmental Impact Assessments	NA	IAIA & GBIF, 2020
A Guide to Biodiversity for the Private Sector	NA	WB, N.D

* "NA" refers to "not available" and "not applicable".

Following the benchmarking analysis conducted in T2.1, WP2, the BioValue project continues the evaluation of environmental assessment instruments in T2.2, WP2 through content analysis of ca. 200 Environmental Impact Assessment and Strategic Environmental Assessment reports with clearly defined selecting criteria in different European countries (e.g. relevance to extensive land use and land conversion, spatial planning, time sensitivity, etc.) in order to understand the status quo of environmental assessment instruments in practice under different circumstances and to

identify the gap between practice and benchmark as well as the potential of further interactions for transformative change⁵.

In the context of WP₃, we will further assess the selected large infrastructure projects from T2.2, WP2⁶ with respect to the following aspects relevant to E&FIs:

- 1) What type of E&FIs is involved and what problem does the E&FI address?
- 2) How does the E&FI relate to the mitigation measures proposed by the environmental assessment? Linking to the following guiding questions for the content analysis on benchmark in T2.2, WP2:
 - *Are mitigation measures suggested for the impact?*
 - *Which type of mitigation measures are suggested?*
- 3) Does the environmental assessment provide information and knowledge on biodiversity and ecosystems that support the design, implementation, and monitoring process of the E&FI? Linking to the following guiding questions for the content analysis on benchmark in T2.2, WP2:
 - *What methodology is used to evaluate the significance of biodiversity impacts in the environmental assessment?*
 - *Which types of parameters are used for evaluating significance of biodiversity impacts in the environmental assessment?*
 - *How are ecosystem services used for working with biodiversity in the environmental assessment?*
 - *How does the environmental assessment specify monitoring of biodiversity impacts?*
- 4) How can the E&FI help promote biodiversity, potentially beyond its original design purpose? E.g., Does the E&FI include clearly identified stewards and beneficiaries, and who are the stewards and beneficiaries? How does the E&FI ensure biodiversity outcomes? Are collective and accumulative impacts considered? Linking to the following guiding questions for the content analysis on causality in T2.2, WP2:
 - *In which phase does the impact unfold?*
 - *Which type of recipient is impacted?*

⁵ For more information, see the BioValue Report D2.2 (to be published by July, 2024).

⁶ Analysis ongoing.

4. Economic and Financial Instruments on the Pathways of Impact towards Transformative Change

In the BioValue project, we further developed the analytical framework for transformative change created by Wittmer et al. (2021) and formulated a BioValue Framework for transformative change that specifically adapts to spatial policy and planning contexts (analysis led by the research team from the Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research- UFZ, for more information see: [BioValue Report D4.1: Analytical framework detailed and specified for application within BioValue](#)). Under the BioValue Framework and in the BioValue Report D4.1, three ambitions have been derived from the underlying causes of degradation and depletion of biodiversity as global commons:

- Ambition 1: Spatial planning safeguards, restores, allows recovery and enhances biodiversity.
- Ambition 2: Spatial planning significantly contributes to balanced and responsible consumption and production without external social and environmental costs.
- Ambition 3: Spatial planning significantly contributes to reducing socioeconomic inequalities.

The three ambitions above form an orientation for the contributions of spatial planning towards transformative change for biodiversity, and the BioValue Report D4.1 illustrates with examples how different pathways of impact can be traced under the context of the three ambitions. In T3.2, WP3, we further analyse the potential of E&FIs to contribute to transformative change for biodiversity by mapping and discussing the generic E&FIs that enhance biodiversity around the examples of impact pathways under the three ambitions (as shown in Figure 1, Figure 2, and Figure 3).

In the context of ambition 1, all the 24 generic E&FIs can intervene at different stages of the impact pathways, as they all have the potential to contribute, to varying degrees, to the restoration, recovery, and enhancement of biodiversity. Taking the example of restricting or prescribing use through protected areas (see Figure 1), the instruments *Allocation of land/resource management & usage rights* and *Privately protected areas & Conservation easements* can be applied at an early stage to establish the ownership of the areas and the corresponding responsibilities of the landowner. With regard to enhanced ecosystem services, instruments such as *Tax reliefs, subsidies, Direct payment, Benefit/revenue-sharing, and Payment for Ecosystem Services* can be employed to encourage biodiversity-friendly management practices to contribute to improving the local biodiversity.

In relation to ambition 2, 19 generic E&FIs are identified as relevant throughout the example of impact pathways (see Figure 2), e.g., using the instruments of *Direct payment* and *Benefit/revenue-sharing* to improve ecosystems for pollinators under urban food production initiatives, establishing *Green credit & loans* or *Green investment facilities (conservation bonds, green investment funds, blended finance, etc.)* for the development in cities to promote green infrastructure and reduce landscape fragmentation.

Regarding ambition 3 on reducing socioeconomic inequalities, we identify 14 E&FIs that clearly define the steward earns and beneficiary and/or polluter pays mechanism of the instrument (see Figure 3). These instruments have a high potential to support the internalisation and distribution of environmental costs and benefits among different types of actors. For example, a *Payments for Ecosystem Services* scheme or a *Benefit/revenue-sharing* project can contribute to reducing socioeconomic inequalities by providing monetary and/or non-monetary compensation from the ecosystem service beneficiaries to the indigenous communities that manage the ecosystems. Above all, the instrument *Environmental training & education programmes* holds a substantial potential across different contexts towards all the three ambitions.

Figure 1: Illustration of different pathways of impact within the context of ambition 1 and how E&FIs can interact (adapted from BioValue Report D4.1).

Figure 2: Illustration of different pathways of impact within the context of ambition 2 and how E&FIs can interact (adapted from BioValue Report D4.1).

Figure 3: Illustration of different pathways of impact within the context of ambition 3 and how E&FIs can interact (adapted from BioValue Report D4.1).

5. Summary and Next Steps

In spatial planning, current recommendations on E&FIs often focus on supporting the implementation of Nature-based Solutions in cities, e.g., through 1) User fees & surcharges; 2) Biodiversity offsets, habitat/ mitigation banking; 3) Green credit & loans; 4) Green investment facilities (conservation bonds, green investment funds, blended finance, etc.); 5) Taxes; 6) Tax reliefs, subsidies; 7) Payments for Ecosystem Services; 8) Allocation of land/resource management & usage rights; 9) Privately protected areas & Conservation easements; and 10) Environmental training & education programmes. The benchmarking of best practice for environmental assessment also includes E&FIs such as 1) Benefit/revenue-sharing; 2) User fees & surcharges; 3) Taxes; 4) Green investment facilities (conservation bonds, green investment funds, blended finance, etc.); 5) Certification & eco-labelling; and 6) Biodiversity offsets, habitat/ mitigation banking. With appropriate design adapted to the biodiversity context, the commonly-applied land value capture tools in spatial planning can be beneficial to promote biodiversity outcomes.

However, in practice, the use of E&FIs in spatial planning is not pronounced in our analysis of selected spatial planning instruments, and so far, addresses only the direct causes of biodiversity loss. Our conceptual analysis along impact pathways identifies current discussions on E&FIs principally located on the impact pathway in the context of ambition 1 on "*spatial planning safeguards, restores, allows recovery and enhances biodiversity*". To address the indirect causes of biodiversity loss, we find 19 out of 24 broader categories of E&FIs that could generate impacts on the pathways towards the ambition 2 on "*spatial planning significantly contributes to balanced and responsible consumption and production without external social and environmental costs*"; and 14 categories of E&FIs for ambition 3 on "*spatial planning significantly contributes to reducing socioeconomic inequalities*". The practical applicability of the E&FIs needs to be tested empirically, e.g., through the BioValue Arenas for Transformation.

As a next step, scheduled for T3.4, WP3, we will work on developing detailed guidance for practitioners on how to select, design, and implement the context-specific instrument. For the BioValue Arenas for Transformation, we will conduct further context analysis of the different arenas for identifying opportunities for E&FI integration.

Annex I: Examples of Land Value Capture Tools in Different Countries

Infrastructure Levy/ Betterment contributions

Portugal: The Encargo de Mais-Valia has been mainly used on a single-case basis, requiring specific legislative authorisation for charging each contribution. For instance, through Decree-Law 46950/1966, when the first bridge connecting the city of Lisbon to the south bank of the Tejo was built, 60% of the estimated land value gains were taxed. More recently, Decree-Law 51/1995 created an exceptional tax for landowners whose land was adjacent to the new bridge built over the Tejo River that lasted 20 years. Besides these cases, the adoption of the tool is rare. Although since 1961, the scope of Encargo de Mais-Valia was widened to charge land value increase resulting from the approval of land use plans, the national government and municipalities rarely implement the instrument and collect the revenues.

Italy: the infrastructure levy (Contributi di Miglioria) is not in force. The principle dates back to the first law on urban planning in 1865 but was only introduced as a formal fiscal instrument in 1931. However, local governments did not use it much due to political unpopularity. Instead, it was replaced by several real estate taxes that do not distinguish between increases in value from specific public infrastructure or planning decisions.

Germany: Landowners pay a levy for public infrastructure renewal and from which they specifically benefit. There are two types of infrastructure levies: Städtebauliche Sanierungsmaßnahmen (URM - urban renewal measures) and Straßenausbaubeiträge (RR - road renewal contributions). URM apply to a wide range of public renewal works, while RR have a narrower scope and only cover public roads' renewal costs near landowners' plots. Some states also have community, or business-improvement-districts laws (BID), where private landowners can initiate public renewal works for which the levies are used.

Denmark: Local governments can charge a levy from property owners for public improvements adjacent to their property, such as green spaces, parks, parking and public transport infrastructures. While Copenhagen adopts the infrastructure levy, the same does not occur in other parts of the country. Through the Copenhagen City & Port Development Corporation or associated community organisation, the municipality charges two types of infrastructure levy: The Metro Fee and the Community Fee. The Metro Fee is charged if a metro station is established within a 50-meter radius of the property. The charge is paid as a property tax increase annually for 60 years after the metro station is created (the values depend on the types of uses). The Community Fee is also charged as an increment to the property tax to support public investment in maintaining public amenities, which create value on private property.

Colombia: The legal basis for the Contribución de Valorización dates back to 1921. It applies to land value increments resulting from public works in roads, public transport systems, public utilities or green spaces. The levy usually corresponds to the estimated total cost of public works, but, in some cases, it's proportional to the land value increment. Recovery of up to 30% of administrative costs is also allowed by law, although local governments usually charge less than 10%. Affected landowners are identified based on market-based approaches that estimate the distance within which public works increase land values. Landowners pay the levy according to a

fixed formula based on the distance to the new infrastructure, location, size, quality, and property value. It has been widely used in large and intermediate cities.

Developer obligations

Portugal: The provision of land for free to the municipality for social land uses (Cedências), and local public infrastructures aim to offset the impact on infrastructure within the project area. Developers must assign areas within the project for major green spaces, public facilities and infrastructure and transfer them to the municipality afterwards. Alternatively, if the designated areas are not transferred, the developer will pay a compensation fee (defined by municipal regulations), in cash or in-kind, off-site the project. Land-use plans should set the criteria to determine the land dedication requirements. Still, municipalities often adopt the standards values prescribed in a national law, which are stated as a proportion of the allowed floor area (e.g. for a residential area of multifamily buildings around 60 m² of land/ 120 m² of floor area). The so-called Municipal Urbanisation Fee (fee for the provision, maintenance and repair, or renewal of major infrastructures) is charged to offset the impact on infrastructure external to the project. The basis for calculating the charge is usually the size and type of development, but additional criteria may apply depending on local ordinances. Although it's a municipal fee, created in order to reinforce local government's autonomy, promote fiscal decentralization and strengthen municipal financial feasibility, a national law establishes the criteria for the definition of the values to be charged. Until 2006, the values charged in most municipalities were clearly insufficient to cover the real municipal expenditure with public infrastructures and facilities (lesser than 20 €/ m² of floor area). According to law in force, Municipal Urbanisation Fee values have now to be justified by an economic and financial rationale and have to take into account the municipal investment plans corresponding to the options defined in land use plans. The fact that revenues are not earmarked (the Constitutional Law in Portugal does not allow it), determines that, very often they are used for purposes different from those that justified its capture.

Italy: The obligations consist of cash or in-kind payments or a combination of both. The "oneri di urbanizzazione and contributo al costo di costruzione" correspond to monetary charges developers pay regarding the public infrastructure and services their developments require. In addition, in local detailed plans for single development areas (piani di lottizzazione convenzionata), developers must directly provide the public infrastructure and services their developments require (roads and basic infrastructure, as well as land for such infrastructure and facilities like schools, libraries, parks and affordable housing). Developments that provide a relevant social benefit may be exempt from payment. Some local governments grant discounts for developments with a high environmental performance. The monetary charges are calculated using a fixed formula, based on the developments' size, type (residential, commercial or industrial), location and quality. The charges follow regional criteria and local regulations. Since regional criteria differ across regions and leave high discretion to local regulations, the charges vary widely across local governments. In general, they cover a low share of the public costs private development generates (in 2018, the average charge per newly built residential unit of 100 m² was EUR 23,000 in Milan and less than 10,000 in Como). The in-kind contributions in local detailed plans are based on national and regional requirements for minimum infrastructure and public space that must be guaranteed to every citizen (standard urbanistic). If local detailed plans require affordable housing, developers typically have to build it inside their project sites. They may negotiate on a case-by-case basis to build affordable housing outside their project sites or

pay in cash instead. National law sets the 'affordability' period at minimum eight years. Local governments may negotiate with developers for longer periods. Some local governments have introduced inclusionary zoning policies in local development plans (Milan's 2012 local development plan required up to 30% of private projects' land for affordable housing). Currently, Emilia-Romagna is the only region with a legal basis for inclusionary zoning. In addition to the above 'regular' obligations, local governments have progressively adopted regulations to obtain an extra contribution from developers for major development or renewal projects. Green areas as well as affordable housing inside or outside project sites are the main matters of negotiations. Moreover, since 2014 national law allows local governments to charge 50% or higher of the land value increase development approvals generate (contributo straordinario per la plusvalenza). Local governments and developers negotiate this contributo straordinario, which is proportional to private profits. Economic feasibility studies should demonstrate the land value increase. However, being discretionary and with regional regulations mostly missing, the contributo straordinario has hardly been used in practice.

Germany: The Building Code (Baugesetzbuch) regulates two types of developer obligations, and local governments implement them as well as receive the revenues. The 'Urban development contracts' (städtebauliche Verträge) cover a wide range of costs generated by private developments and are always applicable. They are based on formulas that consider land size, type and value or negotiated between local governments and developers. Charges usually cover a significant share of public costs (they cannot exceed the total public costs private development generates). Charges can also be paid through affordable housing (e.g., in Frankfurt, 30% of housing units within the project site must be affordable rental units for 20 to 30 years). In addition, Local governments can also charge 'development contributions' (Erschließungsbeiträge) for costs associated with utilities (electricity, gas, water, sewage, telephone and television networks) and for road construction, sidewalks, lighting, green spaces and noise protection systems, near private development. These contributions can amount to 90% of public costs.

Denmark: Developers are subject to obligations to obtain approval for new development or densification. The obligations include in-kind provision of roads, parking, neighbourhood facilities and affordable housing units. Once built, the infrastructure is delivered to local authorities, who will assume the management. Neighbourhood facilities are sometimes handed over to local community organizations. Based on government demand, in every development area, between 25-30% of units must be dedicated to affordable and social housing. However, this value can be negotiated with developers on a case-by-case basis. In some development projects, private ownership and affordable housing are combined in the same area of project development, while in others, the affordable units can be built off-site, anywhere within the jurisdiction. Private developers often negotiate with housing cooperatives (with a long tradition – some have been operating for 150 years) to hand over to them the delivery and management of social housing. All rental revenue is reinvested into the maintenance of the existing housing stock and further affordable and social housing.

United Kingdom: There are different types of developer obligations in each of the UK nations. England and Wales adopt Community Infrastructure Levies (CIL) and Planning Obligations (PO). Scotland only applies Planning Obligations. CIL in England is a fee paid in cash for new developments that create additional floor space of at least 100 m² or new dwellings. There is an established rule to calculate the fee, but differential rates may apply according to the

geographical zone, type or scale of development. Local authorities have discretion about whether or not to exact a CIL. Its purpose is to secure funds for sub-regional or regional infrastructure. Planning Obligations consist of in-kind obligations, or direct financial payments sought to mitigate the impacts of developments and to contribute to community needs, including affordable housing. If a CIL is already in place, a viability assessment study must ensure that the combination of levy and Planning Obligations does not undermine the deliverability of the project. The obligations negotiated with the developer may refer to the provision of land, public space, local infrastructure or affordable housing. Affordable housing units are generally built on-site, but developers may pay to enable the affordable units elsewhere. On small sites, developers may pay in cash, and the local authority builds the units elsewhere, but in many cases, small sites are exempted altogether. The main challenges to implementation are the lack of administrative capacities and the high complexity of operation rules and calculation formulas. Developers sometimes find the charge economically unfeasible and seek to renegotiate it, mainly in places where the real estate market is less dynamic.

Charges for development rights

Portugal: Private developments with a FAR lower than the maximum value allowed that also pursue a public interest (e.g., conservation of nature and biodiversity; safeguarding the natural, cultural or landscape heritage; prevention or minimization of environmental risks; rehabilitation; housing for social purposes; or energy efficiency), may receive a certificate of building rights to be applied on land parcels that are better suited for greater densities. Using the certificate, developers can transfer the unused building rights to other projects, which will then benefit from a higher building quota. The result is that a different project will enjoy extra development rights. Certificates may be exchanged among developers for a monetary value. However, the instrument itself is not paid for in cash. The certificates can only be used during the planning approval process of a development project. The transfer of development rights can also be applied within the context of Land Readjustment (Perequação) applied in defined spatial units (unidades de execução). Municipal land use plans grant all land parcels an equitable share of the abstract development rights proposed by the plan regardless of their effective use. Owners whose abstract developments rights cannot be developed in their original land parcels must be compensated in cash or plots within the development area. The main obstacles for Perequação are the low demand for new private development or densification and local governments' lack of administrative capacity to draw up plans with baseline, maximum and transferable development rights as well as with associated charges for such development rights.

Italy: Landowners who want to develop their plots to meet the local development plans – beyond the baseline development rights but within the maximum density or land use – must pay a cash and in-kind charge (provide land, public infrastructure or services; build affordable housing) for such development rights. The majority of recently approved local development plans (piani regolatori generali) also include the instrument perequazione ('equalisation'), a form of charges for development rights and transferable development rights. In short, local development plans grant all plots the same baseline development rights regardless of their designated use. However, not all plots can be developed. This is to reserve some areas for public uses, such as environmental protection, affordable housing and public facilities. Owners whose plots cannot be developed can transfer the baseline development rights attached to their plots to other plots. The main obstacles for perequazione are the low demand for new private development or

densification and local governments' lack of administrative capacity to draw up plans with baseline, maximum and transferable development rights as well as with associated charges for such development rights.

Denmark: Local governments can charge private developers for an administrative decision to rezone for more profitable uses or higher densities. The charge is paid through the in-kind provision of land or public space or the construction of affordable housing units. No cash substitution is allowed. Local governments make moderate use of this instrument. In the Greater Copenhagen area, value for the % affordable and social housing is of 30% of the total of units, and in the rest of the country it is of 25%. The main challenge to implementation of this type of tool is the low demand for building at higher density in most cities.

Brazil: The Certificates of Additional Construction Potential (known as CEPACs, or Certificados de Potencial Adicional de Construção) are common in large capital cities such as São Paulo, where the real estate market is dynamic, and the Floor Area Ratio (FAR) is low. The charge is often calculated as a proportion of the extra FAR multiplied by the average land price per square meter in some cities. However, in São Paulo and Curitiba charges are defined through an auction market. Development rights can be transferred within the city or a specific zone. The revenues collected are spent throughout the city or invested at designated urban renewal areas called Special Urban Operations (Operações Urbanas Consorciadas). The main implementation challenges are the low demand for building at higher density in smaller cities and the lack of technical capacity to design and implement the charges. Also, there is considerable opposition from landowners and developers, who pressure local governments to reduce or eliminate the charges. Furthermore, the low quality of land registries and reduced political will constitute additional obstacles to implementation.

Land readjustment

Portugal: According to the 1999 National legal framework, the land readjustment objectives are: to redistribute the gains and charges assigned by land-use plans to landowners; to provide for municipal land or buildings for public infrastructures and facilities; to avoid speculative behaviours like land hoarding; and to increase municipal financial resources. Land readjustment is initiated either by landowners' initiative or in cooperation with the Local government. Ideally, it's implemented in detailed plans (Plano de Pormenor) due to its specific nature, contents, and scale. Still, it can also occur within spatial units (unidades de execução) only framed by municipal master plans or urban zoning plans. The consent of all involved landowners is required. When that does not happen, municipalities may carry expropriations of land at market value. This alternative implies a strong political and financial commitment and the capability to bear all the risks (namely, not recovering the public investment), given the high costs often implicated in the expropriation processes. Around 30% of the readjusted land is reserved for public infrastructures or facilities. In the end, the serviced plots are allocated to the original landowners or private investors, as close as possible to their original land, according to the previously defined compensation rules. The National law defines compensation mechanisms but they are neither mandatory nor quantified. The proposed mechanisms include the average FAR, for the distribution of benefits, and the local infrastructures costs allocation. Other compensation rules can be established, provided that the equity principle is respected. When some landowners fail to collaborate, municipalities must apply expropriation.

The challenges to implementation are low levels of technical, and administrative capacities, low quality of land registries, the high costs of expropriations and the absence of a rising real estate market.

Italy: The legal basis dates back to 1942, and the current national legal framework for land readjustment was introduced in 1967. Local governments and private landowners can initiate a land readjustment project through a local detailed plan (piano di lottizzazione convenzionata). However, the consent of landowners whose parcels represent at least 51% of the readjustment areas' value is required. Landowners who do not consent can be expropriated. Land is valued based on the cadastral taxable value at the time of presentation of the readjustment plan. This allows recovering the increase in land values readjustment projects generate. Landowners must provide land for public infrastructure and facilities according to the national requirements for minimum public space that must be guaranteed (standard urbanistici). Local development plans (piani regolatori generali) may set higher requirements for local detailed plans. In recent plans, landowners often had to provide up to 50% of readjustment areas for public infrastructure and facilities. After land readjustment, landowners receive plots (superficie fondiaria) corresponding to their building rights. They can also exchange reallocated plots for cash. Private developers can buy readjusted plots. The main obstacle can be the length and bureaucracy to strike an agreement between landowners and the local government, which is needed for land readjustment.

Germany: Land readjustment (Umlegung) was first introduced in 1902 in the city of Frankfurt to regulate the transformation of rural properties into new urban plots. However, the national legal basis dates back to 1960 (when land readjustment was used extensively in the post-war reconstruction) and is now included in the Building Code (Baugesetzbuch), which regulates the mandatory land readjustment (amtliche Baulandumlegung). The rationale behind land readjustment is that urban development has a social purpose that cannot be wasted. Therefore, urban land shouldn't remain idle because of inappropriate property patterns. It is a specific obligation, implicit in the landowner's property rights, to help prepare land for urban development. In order to implement binding land-use plans (Bebauungsplan), the law empowers municipal governments to enforce land readjustment whenever the shape or size of the initial properties don't match with the proposed plots or when landowners cannot overcome conflicts in the negotiation process. Despite the above, land readjustment is mainly implemented in German through voluntary negotiations, not government imposition. However, voluntary land readjustment (freiwilliger Baulandumlegung) often takes the form of consented mandatory land readjustment so that landowners can profit from some of the advantages offered by the compulsory process (fiscal benefits, access to local government technical expertise and reduction in development time). After land readjustment, landowners receive plots with a value proportional to their original holdings. If all original parcels have a similar value per m², they may be reallocated based on area rather than value. Landowners usually receive plots located on or as close as possible to their original land. Owners of readjusted plots that are less valuable than the original parcels are compensated in cash. However, landowners of readjusted plots that are more valuable are not required to pay any compensation.

Denmark: Land readjustment projects are mainly carried out for urban expansion or renewal on derelict or abandoned public land. The government acquires private property at market value, and the participation of the included private landowners is compulsory. The involvement of resisting owners in projects of public interest is enforced through expropriations. Land is pooled

together, rezoned and divided. After land readjustment, the land can be sold in the private market or used to implement major development projects of public interest, as was the case for the city-wide metro system financed by the urban developments of Copenhagen City & Port Development Corporation. A share of the readjusted plots is reserved for public improvements, such as public roads, public transportation, parks and green space – from which landowners will benefit. In addition, the land readjustment project typically reserves plots for future sales, to generate additional public revenues.

Japan: The first land readjustment project (Kukaku-Seiri) was implemented in 1870 in Kobe. Many other land readjustment projects in rural and urban areas took place in the following decades, but only in 1954 was the first Land Readjustment Act enacted. Since then, land readjustment has been used for urban expansion, urban development or renewal, disaster prevention and reconstruction to a great extent. Besides local government, private entities, landowners, and associations can initiate land readjustment, but at least two-thirds of the involved landowners' consent is needed. Typically, 30-40% of readjusted plots are reserved for public improvements, including infrastructure and utilities. Newly readjusted areas also typically include publicly owned plots for sale, which are used to recover development costs. After readjustment, landowners receive plots with a value proportional to the original holdings, preferably in the same location or as close as possible. Developers can also receive readjusted plots in return for their investment in the project. If the final plots are smaller than a specific size or are less valuable than the original land parcels, landowners can be compensated. However, if the readjusted plots are more valuable than the original ones, they are not required to pay any compensation to the public authorities.

Annex II: Overview of the Spatial Planning Instruments with Transformative Elements on “Actions/Instruments/Regulations”

Country	Spatial Planning Instrument	Year of development/adoption
Italy	Regional Territorial Plan of Emilia Romagna	2010
Italy	Territorial Metropolitan Plan of Bologna	2021
Italy	Urban Plan of Bologna Municipality	2021
Denmark	Action Plan of the Copenhagen Municipal Biodiversity Strategy	2022
Denmark	Municipal Spatial Plan for Skive Municipality	2016
Denmark	Framework Local Plan for GreenLab Area in Skive Municipality	2016
Germany	Berlin Strategy: Urban Development Concept Berlin 2030	2015
Germany	Land Use Plan of Berlin	2015
Germany	City Development Mobility and Transport Plan of Berlin 2030	2021
Germany	City Development Plan Climate: Securing Urban Quality of Life in Climate Change (Berlin)	2011
Portugal	General Law of Public Policies for Soil, Territorial Development, and Urbanism	2014
Portugal	Portuguese Legal Framework of Territorial Management Instruments	2015
Portugal	National Program of Territorial Planning Policy	2019
Portugal	Regional Program of the Lisbon Metropolitan Area	2002
Portugal	Management Plan of the Arrábida Natural Park	2005
Portugal	Municipal Master Plan of Setúbal	2021
Scotland	National Planning Framework	2023
Scotland	Scottish Planning Policy	2014
Scotland	Cairngorms National Park Local Development Plan 2020	2020
Spain	Regional Planning Guidance of the Basque Country	2019
Spain	Partial Territorial Plan of Central Álava	2022- revision of the plan of 2004
Spain	General Urban Development Plan of Vittoria-Gasteiz	2023- revision of the plan of 2001
Switzerland	Territorial Plan Switzerland	2012
Switzerland	Cantonal-Ticino Master Plan Revision (explanatory Report)	2009
Switzerland	Municipal action program (city of Bellinzona)	2020

* For more details on the spatial planning instruments, see: *BioValue Report D1.1: Current Challenges and Barriers to Biodiversity Inclusion in SP&MI*

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